

MooringSense – GA 851703

Mooring System Integrity Management through Monitoring, Digital Twin and Control Technologies for Cost Reduction and Increased Efficiency

D8.1 Version 2.0

Communication Plan I

Actual Date of Delivery:	2020-03-10
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Work package:	WP8 – Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation
Security:	PU
Nature:	R
Version:	2.0
Total number of pages:	24

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 851703

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Document Control

Version	Details of Change	Author	Approved	Date
1.0	Document Created	MC	AP	24.01.20
2.0	Include disclaimer	AP	AP	10.03.20

Executive Summary

This document contains the MooringSense Communication Plan, which has been designed to be in line with the definition provided by the H2020 programme and the contractual obligations. It includes the description of MooringSense communication strategy, the project visual identity and communication material.

Since communication actions and dissemination activities can overlap and make use of the same tools, the present document is complemented with the Dissemination and Exploitation Plan.

To allow continuous Communication Plan adaptation, the initially defined plan will be updated twice along the project duration, in Months 12 and 24.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Term	Description
B2B	Business to business
EERA	European Energy Research Alliance
EU	European Union
FOW	Floating Offshore Wind
FOWT	Floating Offshore Wind Turbine
H2020	Horizon 2020
INEA	Innovation and Networks Executive Agency
IPR	Intellectual Property Right
JP	Joint Programme
OPEX	Operational Expenditure
OW	Offshore Wind
O&G	Oil and gas
O&M	Operation and Maintenance
RDI	Research, Development and Innovation
R&I	Research and Innovation
SME	Small and medium enterprise
SHM	Structural Health Monitoring
URL	Universal Resource Locator
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

The effective MooringSense communication requires to set strategic measures to reach a multitude of audiences beyond the project own community (e.g. industrial and scientific communities), including the media and the public in general. At this regard, it is considered of paramount importance to reach out to the European society in order show the impact and benefits of EU-funded research and innovation activities, and how MooringSense addresses societal challenges related to decarbonization and energy security, providing innovative solutions with high impact.

1.1 Purpose and scope

The purpose of the MooringSense's Communication Plan is to define the set of actions and measures, as well as the communication material to be used in the promotion of the project and its results during the whole lifetime of the action. Consequently, this first version of the Communication Plan (M3) will be updated twice during the project lifetime, in M12 and M24.

The first version of the Communication Plan covers:

- The communication strategy definition, where main objectives, key message and ideas and target audience are identified.
- The communication channels and material: visual identity, guidelines, project website, posters, leaflets, templates, newsletters, social networks, videos, press releases and workshops).
- The definition of metrics and targets to be used to assess the communication activity and its results.
- A planification of the communication activities.

1.2 Intended audience / Classification

This document is intended for all project partners, WP leaders and WP participants. The document is also intended for use outside the project, it is therefore classified as a public document.

Relevant parts of this study can however be used in public documents.

1.3 Application documents

Inputs from the following documents were used as a source of information for preparing this document:

Table 1.1: Application documents

REF	Document
AD-01	Grant Agreement – 851703 - MooringSense
AD-02	Consortium Agreement – MooringSense

1.4 Reference documents

The following list contains references to other deliverables of the MooringSense project mentioned in the present document, where complementary information can be found:

Table 1.2: Application documents

REF	Document
RD-01	D8.6 Communication and Dissemination Report on Activities

1.5 Document structure

The document is structured in the following sections:

- Section 2 provides a brief description of the methodology.
- Section 3 describes the MooringSense communication strategy through the identification of main objectives, key message and target audience.
- Section 4 provides detailed information about the commercial material that will be used in the project
- Section 5 details the metrics that will be used for the assessment of communication activities
- Section 6 provides the GANTT of the communication action plan

2. Methodology

In addition to dissemination of MooringSense project results, partners will make a remarkable effort to effectively communicate the project and its impacts. All the communication activities will be accomplished through a specific communication plan that will be designed and implemented within the project. This plan intends to be used by the MooringSense project partners as a guide to develop their individual and collective communication activities according to the communication strategy defined.

The communication plan described in this document comprises a wide variety of measures to ensure the fulfilment of communication objectives, as well as, the definition of metrics to enable the communication success assessment.

Finally, the communication plan will be updated along the project to ensure the achievement of communication targets. Plan updates have been scheduled with the following calendar:

Figure 2.1: Communication Plan updates

3. Communication Strategy

3.1 Objectives

The communication strategy of MooringSense project has three main goals:

1. **Project traceability:** Tracing the project implies constantly and coherently communicating its development, the main milestones reached and the most relevant results. Openness has been a priority, but at the same time issues regarding IPR protection will be taken into account.
2. **Broader socialization.** Technological innovations and cost reductions achieved by the European industry has paved the way for the wind energy sector to emerge as a strategic sector for the European economy and for its growth and decarbonization. However, proactive innovation is still needed to keep the EU wind industry's competitive edge and technology innovation efforts. The socialization goals can be stated as:
 - a) EU R&I strategy and MooringSense alignment (e.g. improving operation and maintenance via digitization).
 - b) Public funding leveraged to unlock private investment in R&I.
 - c) Remove barriers regarding social acceptance of FOW.
3. **Raise awareness** of the paramount importance for Europe of wind energy, in particular the OW energy, as a strategic sector for the European economy and for the wellbeing and prosperity of European societies.

The present Communication Plan details the instruments intended to be used by the MooringSense consortium to ensure the above mentioned goals. Communication activities will be continuously monitored and reported with detail in RD-01 (D8.6 Communication and Dissemination Report on Activities).

3.2 Key message

The key message is that the MooringSense project will help to reduce the cost associated to the production of offshore energy, enhancing the shift from production from fossil to renewable energy sources and contributing to solve the global climate and energy challenges.

Through the development of more efficient strategies and tools for mooring system integrity and control, MooringSense aims at reducing FOW operational costs by 10-15% and to increase the Annual Energy Production by 2-3%.

Key facts/ideas:

- O&M costs in FOW farms can range between 6% and 20% of the whole Life Cycle Cost depending on site conditions and the FOWT technology concept. At the same time, maintenance accounts for the largest portion of O&M effort, cost and risk.
- MooringSense will foster the shift from unscheduled maintenance to schedule maintenance, since scheduled maintenance results in reduced costs of services and optimized availability (less downtime).
- Mooring systems failure statistics in the O&G sector show unexpected high failure rates. From this data, it can be derived that there is a high degree of uncertainty related to mooring systems performance and O&M costs. Even more if we considered the higher complexity of FOWT loading conditions.
- Current control strategies are conservative and control parameters are tuned in a not coordinated way along the wind farm. On the other hand, FOWT components are sized to withstand the worst-case extreme and fatigue loads. If more holistic control strategies were developed and applied it could lead to improved operation of FOW farms and increased efficiency, since an optimal balance between loads and energy production could be reached.

3.3 Target Audience

To ensure the maximum effectiveness of the communication plan, potential interested parties have been identified and grouped, in order to address specific messages via the optimal channels:

Table 3.1: Communication targets and appropriate communication tools

Stakeholders	Objectives [Impact]	Communication Activity/Channel
General public	To raise project awareness [Low]	Visual identity; Website; Infographic video; Brochures, flyers, leaflets; Press releases; Social media: YouTube, Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn. In addition to the above mentioned channels: Public deliverables; Demonstrators; Workshops; In addition to the above mentioned channels: B2B meetings with experts and relevant stakeholders.
Green organizations	To inform about environmental aspects [Medium]	
EU/International associations or platforms in the Energy Sector.	To inform about the latest advancements of research in the field [Medium]	
Governmental agencies & regulatory bodies	To have their support, as their impact is high [High]	
Scientific community	To exchange knowledge, research findings and best practices developed in related projects [High]	
Industry/SME and Advisory Board	Create potential commercialization opportunities with stakeholders [High]	

The main roles of the project target groups are as follows:

Table 3.2: Preliminary Communication Plan

Audience	General public	Green organizations	EU/International associations	Public bodies	Scientific community	Industry/SME and Advisory Board
Increase project visibility	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Give input/feedback on project development	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Generate Market opportunities	X	✓	✓	X	X	✓
Support project development	X	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Advance Collaboration	X	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

According to the different target groups and communication objectives identified, the following activities are planned:

- **Objective 1: Improving Competitiveness and Market Uptake**

To WHOM	WHY and WHAT	HOW
Industry-FOW operators and service providers	Inform potential customers about benefits and potentials of the MooringSense development and receive feedbacks from an end-user point of view	Direct contact with end-users in workshops , discussions with the industrial partners (Advisory Board), dedicated information on brochures , website, presentations in relevant European and National associations (EERA JP WIND ...), participation in exhibition events.
Industry - European OW	Increase critical mass on the market, identify potential synergies, foster wider commercialisation of results, establish cooperation relations and maximize and extend project impacts.	Dedicated workshops, conferences and brochures . Participation in EU (Wind Europe, Vanguard Initiative, EERA JP WIND and JP OCEAN) and national associations (e.g. Reoltec, Enermar, Belgian Energy Research Alliance...). MooringSense will participate actively at key conferences and exhibition EU events about Wind Energy.
Industry - Investors, Banks, Insurance	Provide awareness & means for reducing OPEX and life cycle cost efficiency.	Specific meetings with the participation of contractors/investors as Equinor, EDF, Members of the MooringSense Advisory Board, Worley Parsons, Navantia, DNV GL, NREL and Dragados Offshore in dedicated meetings.

- **Objective 2: Improving Public Perception and Societal image**

To WHOM	WHY and WHAT	HOW
General public - European citizens, Green Organizations, Public Bodies and Scientific community in general.	Make wider community aware of impact of EU research, Energy Union Strategy and the strategic targets related to OW. Improve public image of OW technology. Enable contacts with the project partners.	MooringSense website; press releases; social media (e.g. Facebook, Twitter, and LinkedIn); project dissemination material; creation of MooringSense infographic video (YouTube, exhibitions...), interviews in local media and science magazines. Links with consortium members' activities for the promotion of scientific culture and new clean energy technologies
Scientific Community - Other R&D initiatives and project consortia	Use synergies, e.g. joint resources; uptake of suitable external developments. Exchange of results in other OW projects, and cooperative work.	Networks and websites, participation in CSAs, joint workshops , cross-project partner networks, joint conferences, cooperation agreements with other H2020 projects.

Scientific Community	Attract young people; Inform about job opportunities; Improve technical skills for under- post-graduate students.	Training material, presentations at universities, twinning projects, internal placements for students, newsletters to target groups and technical public information.
Other sectors	Get information on latest development and available new solutions; Initiate cooperation with other industry sectors such as O&G, offshore aquaculture or shipping/shipbuilding.	Desk research, networks of the MooringSense partners who are active in other synergetic sectors (e.g. Intecsea, Vicinay and Bridon-Bekaert for O&G, Sintef Ocean for aquaculture and ocean energy, and also TNO for environmental issues).

- **Objective 3: Removing external barriers towards application**

To WHOM	WHY and WHAT	HOW
Cross-industry standards (ISO, Class Societies,	Transmit findings and needs of standards to increase critical mass across sectors.	Participation in meetings in standard committees on EU and national level, facing similar challenges & barriers (technical, environmental, social acceptance, etc....)
Research Administration and funding authorities	Ensure consideration of achievements and RDI needs for future research programmes.	Public deliverables and reports to EU associations, contact with national governments

4. Communication Channels and Material

4.1 Visual Identity

In line with the H2020 visual guidelines, a visual identity has been created for the project, comprising a logo and style in different formats.

The logo has been designed as a word-picture-brand, taking into account the planned usage in both printed and digital media. The logo is built around the project name, including a clear symbol of both mooring lines and floating offshore wind turbines.

It is a very recognizable and eye-catching logo, easy to identify and will ease the project identification by the public:

Figure 4.1: MooringSense logo

On the other hand, selected pantone will help the final user to identify the application environment of the developed technology as a marine application. This colour palette will be applied to the different documents' templates:

Table 1 MooringSense logo Pantone

	RGB
	151; 182; 217
	106; 137; 187
	45; 77; 139

4.2 Communication Guidelines

4.2.1 INEA communication guidelines

The intention of these guidelines is to maintain coherence and uniformity in our dissemination and at the same time ensure compliance to EU requirements. These guidelines are based on the communication obligations signed on the Grant Agreement.

Mandatory (as in grant agreement)

- Before engaging in a communication activity, the beneficiaries must inform the Coordinator, that will inform the Agency.
- Communication material shall always display the EU emblem prominently. See https://europa.eu/european-union/abouteuropa/legal_notices_en for more information on the use of the European emblem;

Figure 4.2: EU emblem reproductions in black & white, 2 colours white & blue and colour reproduction

- Communication material shall always include the following text:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 851703

- Any communication activity must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the agency, and the Commission are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

4.2.2 MooringSense additional communication guidelines

In addition to the required, recommended and optional guidelines by the Commission, the project has confirmed their own guidelines. When in doubt or in the unexpected case of conflict, Commission guidelines always have priority.

- *Notification prior to dissemination*
All communication activities will be announced prior to dissemination to the Project Coordinator at: WP8@mooringsense.com.
- *Reference to website*
All dissemination activities will refer to the website URL of the project; All project members will ensure that their communication activity or product is also recorded on the MooringSense website: www.mooringsense.eu
- *Compliance to style*
In communication activities where project members present the project or on behalf of the project, all will use the MooringSense house style as much as possible over the affiliations house style (logo, and templates)

4.3 Partners Website

All the partners will include a mention to the MooringSense project and their contribution on their respective websites:

Partner	Website publication
CTC	https://centrotecnologicocctc.com/2019/11/12/mooringsense/
SAITEC	https://www.saitec.es/en/noticias/noticia26.html
ZUNIBAL	https://zunibal.com/en/mooringsense/
TNO	https://www.tno.nl/en (*)
VICINAY	https://www.vicinaymarine.com (*)
IKERLAN	https://www.ikerlan.es/noticias
SINTEF OCEAN	https://www.sintef.no/en/ocean/offshore-wind/#News (*)
BWRI	https://www.bekaert.com (*)
INTECSEA	http://www.intecsea.com (*)

(*) In preparation on the moment of delivery of this deliverable

4.4 Project Website

One of the main communication channels of the MooringSense project will be the website. The project website will serve as a central point for all public materials: links to relevant events or publications related to the project, notes about events where consortium members are participating, press releases, news on the field, documentation generated by the project like public deliverables, online versions of any leaflets or posters, and other useful material like possible videos of eventual integration tests. Besides, the main language in the website is English, which facilitates its wider diffusion in the EU.

The site will be structured in the following sections and with the following contents:

Table 2 MooringSense website content

Page tab	Content
HOME	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Landing page. Eye-catching images, MooringSense Key message, feed of social networks last updates. - Links to social networks and YouTube channel
About (about the project):	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Project main objectives - Technology - Consortium description (it will include main contacts for the project)
MooringSense project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Description of WPs - Progress - to be updated with project current status, last achievements and next steps
Publications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Communication and dissemination material - Public deliverables

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Green access publications - Public datasets - Newsletters and communication material
Events and News	<p>Agenda of congresses, events, workshops related to the MooringSense technologies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Self-generated news about the project (updates, advancements, results etc.) <p>Twitter, Facebook feeds and other social media captures</p>
Contact	It will include a unique email address (info@mooringsense.eu) and the physical address of CTC

The domain www.mooringsense.eu has been registered and the website will be fully available and fully operative on April 2020. The project's website will remain available for at least one year after project's conclusion. Then, the results will be migrated to regular parts of the web communication available to the partners.

4.5 Posters, leaflets and document templates

Following the visual identity, the following tools will be produced:

- Document templates: Deliverables, PowerPoint presentations, poster template.
- Leaflets and poster: Two versions of leaflets and poster will be produced:
 - o An initial version with a description of the main goals of the project, the consortium, the technologies involved and the main results expected.
 - o Second version that will be updated along the project duration with the last achievements information.

All these elements will be generated in line with the Communication Guidelines described in section 4.2 Communication Guidelines.

4.6 Newsletter

Periodic newsletters will be sent to target groups and technical public. The service will be part of the project website and will inform all the interested stakeholders during the project lifetime. Newsletters content will include:

- Project status update
- Future events where the consortium will participate
- Future events related with the project developments
- News related to the project topics

4.7 Social Networks

To increase the impact of the communication strategy, profiles on social networks will be created. Social networks have the power to achieve a multiplier promotional effect on communication activities and will create straight communication channels to interact with the audience. Frequent updates of these channels are expected, in order to guarantee their growth and to achieve a significant number of followers to maximise the impact. The main updates to be published in Social Networks will consist in:

- Inform periodically about the research activity is being carried out.
- Announce the release of public deliverables
- Inform about events (fairs, congress, etc.) where consortium is participating

- Inform about main project achievements and dissemination activity
- Photos of project review meetings
- Sharing of FOW important news

Channel	Link
FACEBOOK	https://www.facebook.com/MooringSense/
TWITTER	https://twitter.com/MooringSense
LINKEDIN	<p>MooringSense Project group</p> <p>As a first step, a MooringSense group has been created. The main advantage is that we will take advantage of our professional connections to reach a bigger audience from the very beginning.</p>

Also, the following considerations will be taken into account regarding hashtags and tags:

- **Mandatory:**
 - The use of Hashtags and tags referring to the EU is mandatory
 - The mention of the profiles of involved partners is mandatory (those having active profile).
- **Recommended:**
 - Hashtags of key words related to the publication content are recommended

The following table shows the different social networks and their direct links, as well as the different hashtags to be used:

Channel	Mandatory	Recommended
FACEBOOK	#H2020 @EU_H2020 @centrotecnologicoCTC @ZunibaSL @TNOresearch @sintefocean @BridonBekaert (SAITEC, IKERLAN and INTECSEA not available)	#mooringsystems #O&M #offshore #floatingwind #windenergy #integritymanagement
TWITTER	#H2020 @EU_H2020 @saitecoffshore @zunibal_SL @TNO_nieuws @IKERLAN_official @SINTEF_Ocean @INTECSEA_WP	#mooringsystems #O&M #offshore #floatingwind #windenergy #integritymanagement

	@BridonBekaert (CTC, VICINAY not available)	
LINKEDIN	#H2020 @EU_H2020 @Centro Tecnológico CTC @Saitec Offshore @Zunibal @TNO @Vicinay Marine Innovacion @IKERLAN @Sintef Ocean @Intecsea @Bridon-Bekaert The Ropes Group	#mooringsystems #O&M #offshore #floatingwind #windenergy #sath #integritymanagement

All the partners will follow the mentioned social networks from their respective organizational accounts and will share and recommend the content to promote the MooringSense networks.

4.8 Videos

A YouTube channel will be created to allocate the project videos. The videos will have a maximum duration of 3 minutes and will clearly update the general public about the main goals and project achievements. Given that the videos will be addressed to general audience, very simple language will be used and they will include subtitles to enable their diffusion during events or fairs.

At least the following videos are expected:

Video	Content
1	- Project and consortium presentation - Motivation behind the project - Expected impacts
2	- Including Water Tank tests images (M22)
3	- MooringSense solutions integrated and validates (M34)

These YouTube video links will be shared using the video showcase EU service¹. By means of this service, videos are added to the EU-funded R&I projects YouTube Playlist² and also they are promoted via the social media channels (@EUScienceInnov - Twitter, Facebook, YouTube).

Furthermore, the videos will also be shared through the project social networks.

4.9 Press Releases

With the spirit of making the consortium members and the project better known by the general public (i.e. European citizens, green organizations, public bodies and scientific community in general), as well as FOW Industry in general, several press releases will be made throughout the duration of the project.

Coinciding with the expected project meetings, press releases will be launched in the following dates, including relevant updates about the status of the project:

Press Release	Main content	Due date month
PR1	Kick off	M1
PR2	MooringSense Architecture	M7
PR3	MooringSense Specification	M12
PR4	Validated Numerical Models and Tank Testing Data	M19
PR5	Validated SHM system prototype	M24
PR6	Decision Support Tool	M30
PR7	Validated Test Execution Result	M36

All partners will publish project results in local and international press: press releases, newsletters in magazines and newspapers etc. Moreover, all beneficiaries will use their own communication portals to include the main information about the project and its results.

Furthermore, the following distribution channels will be exploited by the partners to maximize the impact of the press releases generated:

- Local agencies

A list of local communication agencies will be created and updated during the project development. Press releases will be also sent to these agencies to maximize the impact and to increase the awareness of European citizens.

- EC's media channels:
 - <https://horizon-magazine.eu/>
 - <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/newsroom/551/>
 - <https://cordis.europa.eu/news/en>

4.10 Workshops

Three workshops, at least, will be organized and conducted during the course of the project. These workshops will be scheduled and organized as side events at relevant international events or at MooringSense progress meetings.

Some topics has been already identified together with tentative dates:

1 Calling all EU-funded R&I projects: <http://ec.europa.eu/research/investeuresearch/index.cfm>

2 EU-funded R&I projects Play list <https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLvpwjZTs-LjHDvRTqlyjfLeflXDak5er>

1. Mooring system digital twin and model testing (M18)
2. Mooring systems integrity management under risk-based approach (M24).
3. Virtual mooring line tension measurement and SHM. (M30)
4. Final workshop: MooringSense solutions, tools and impacts (M35)

4.11 Publications and participation in events

Scientific publications and the participation of MooringSense's consortium in international events will be key dissemination activities. However, this kind of activities are able to maximize the impact of communication. A preliminary list of publications and participations in congresses is included below:

Highlights of planned dissemination channels			
Event/Journal	Countries addressed	Type of Audience	Date (planned or expected)
Floating Offshore. Wind Turbine Conference	Global	Floating Offshore Wind	2021-2023
Offshore Energy Exhibition and Conference	Europe	O&G, OW, marine energy	2021-2023
RINA - Royal Institution of Naval Architects	Europe	Marine vessels and structures	2023
OMAE Conference on Ocean, Offshore & Arctic Engineering	Global	Ocean and offshore engineering	2022
OTC - Offshore Technology Conference	Global	Offshore energy	2021
Wind Energy	Global		2023
Ocean Engineering. ISSN: 0029-8018	Global	Offshore platforms. Moorings	2022
Applied Ocean Research ISSN 0141-1187	Global	Floating system hydrodynamics	2023
Journal of Ocean Engineering and Marine Energy. ISSN: 2198-6452	Global	Coastal and offshore engineering, marine renewable energy	2023
WindEurope Conference & Exhibition	Europe	Wind Energy	2021-2023
Journal on Environmental Degradation of Materials and its Control. ISSN: 0010-938X	Global	Corrosion and its control	2022
Marine Structures . ISSN: 0951-8339	Global	Design, fabrication and O&M	2023
GPS Solutions . ISSN 1521-1886	Global	GNSS solutions	2023
The Jo. of Navigation . ISSN 1469-7785	Global	Navigation systems	2022
IAIN Institutes of Navigation	Global	Navigation systems	2023

IEEE/ION-PLANS Position Location and Navigation Symposium	Global	Navigation systems and applications	2022
ICL-GNSS Localization and GNSS	Europe	GNSS solutions and systems	2021
TORQUE	Europe	Wind Energy	2022
Wind Energy Science Conference	Europe	Wind Energy	2021, 2023
EERA-JP WIND	Europe	Wind Energy Association	2021-2023

5. Metrics

Regarding communication activity, measurable target results have been defined:

Communication Activity	Channel	Target Metric
Visual Identity	Logo and templates	1 of each
Website	Project Website	>5000 visitors
Posters and Leaflets	Posters	≥3
	Printed Leaflets	>500 leaflets distributed
Newsletters	Newsletters	≥6
Social Networks	Facebook	>200 followers >20 posts
	Twitter	>200 followers >20 posts
	LinkedIn Group	>100 members >20 posts
Videos	YouTube channel	≥3
Press Releases	Press releases in printed and web media	>20
Workshops	Side/parallel events at international conferences or progress meetings	≥3
Advisory Board meetings	Side events during MooringSense progress meetings	≥3

